

Experimental relationship between compressional wave attenuation and surface strains in brittle rock

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Abstract

Linear ultrasonic testing (LUT) has been extensively used as a tool for the evaluation of damage processes in various materials ranging from synthetic metals to natural geomaterials, such as rocks. A key limitation of LUT-based damage studies to date is the lack of explicit evidence used in associating material damage with the changes in measured LUT attributes (e.g. ultrasonic wave amplitude and velocity). In this study, the evolution of the full-field strains in brittle rock specimens (Lyons sandstone) subjected to failure are analyzed in real-time and linked with the changes in the ultrasonic wave amplitude in localized areas illuminated by ultrasonic beams, termed as the Ultrasonic Image Areas (UIAs). The non-contact optical full-field displacement measurement method of 2D-DIC (Digital Image Correlation) is implemented in combination with the LUT procedure to continuously track changes in the ultrasonic wave amplitude with the evolution of strains across the surface of the uniaxially loaded intact rock specimens. The ultrasonic amplitude showed near-linear correlation with the intensity of inelastic tensile strain recorded in the rock specimens. The results from the study corroborate that the ultrasonic changes are in-fact influenced by the regions of tensile cracking, which is the primary inelastic deformation mechanism in brittle rocks.

Keywords

Digital Image Correlation, Brittle Rock, Ultrasonic Wave Propagation, Uniaxial Loading

1. INTRODUCTION

Linear ultrasonic testing (LUT) is one of the most widely used non-destructive methods for characterization of rock damage processes, particularly because of the sensitivity of the ultrasonic waves to manifest microcracking related damage (Achenbach, 1990; Aydin, 2013). LUT results are only valid for implicit qualitative conclusions, as it is difficult to explicitly measure the strain-related damage distribution in real-time throughout rock specimens under load (Philippidis & Aggelis, 2005; Aggelis & Shiotani, 2007; Peng et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2018). In order to better understand the capability of the ultrasonic waves to detect damage in geomaterials, it is of interest to explicitly correlate the changes in LUT attributes with the indicators of rock structural integrity (e.g. microcracks, regions of strain concentration) (Harnett et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018). With this goal in mind, the evolution of full-field strains from uniaxially loaded prismatic intact rock specimens has been recorded in real-time using the 2D-Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique, and concurrently, the changes in ultrasonic wave amplitude have been recorded in the present study. The prismatic shape of specimens has been chosen to ensure a planar surface necessary for accurate in-plane 2D-DIC measurements (Ferrero et al., 2008; Sutton et al., 2009).

Extensive work has been performed using LUT as a tool for diagnosing the state of damage in various applications (Jones, 1952; Suaris & Fernando, 1987; Pyrak-Nolte, 1988; Sayers et al., 1990; Scott et al., 1993; Cai & Zhao, 2000; Hildyard et al., 2005; Zhao et al., 2006; Acosta-Colon et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2014; Hedayat et al., 2014a; Ghazvinian, 2015; Modiriasari et al., 2017; Gheibi & Hedayat, 2018; Hedayat et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018). Significant efforts have been made to analytically model the effects of cracks and fractures on the ultrasonic wave propagation (Waterman & Truell, 1961; O'Connell & Budianski, 1974; Piau, 1979; Crampin et al., 1980; Hudson, 1981; Pyrak-Nolte et al., 1990a, b; Gross & Zhang, 1992; Yang & Turner, 2003; Chaix et al., 2006; Blum et al., 2011; De Basabe et al., 2016). These analytical models can be broadly categorized as the displacement discontinuity model (DDM) (Mindlin, 1960; Schoenberg, 1980; Pyrak-Nolte, 1988) and the equivalent medium model (EMM) (Waterman & Truell, 1961; Crampin, 1981; Hudson, 1981) based on the fracture size and spacing in relation to the ultrasonic wavelength (Perino et al., 2010). These analytical models facilitate fundamental understanding of the effect of cracks/fractures on the characteristics of wave propagation. Numerical methods provide an alternative approach to simulate the problems involving wave propagation through damaged media. Continuum and discontinuum based numerical models have been used for simulating wave behavior in fractured medium in several studies (Kelner, 1999; Hildyard, 2007; Parastatidis et al., 2017; Yu et al., 2017). The advantage of numerical methods lies in the fact that they can handle complicated problems and can give highly accurate results; however, the reliability of numerical simulations is highly dependent on the

numerical representation of the damaged medium (e.g. the constitutive laws and the boundary conditions, material behavior etc.) (Su et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2018).

Experiments can serve as a fundamental and reliable approach for studying the phenomenon of wave propagation through a damaged rock medium (Yang et al., 2018). In order to experimentally verify the wave propagation behavior in a damaged medium, it is crucial to define the relevant scale of damage, because the mechanism of wave interaction with damage is dependent on the wavelength (λ) of the probing ultrasonic wave as compared with the scale of damage (Yin et al., 1995; Garnier et al., 2003). Damage in rocks (where D is the size of the damage features) can be macroscopic ($D \gg \lambda$) or microscopic ($D \ll \lambda$) depending on the scale of damage with respect to the wavelength of the probing ultrasonic wave (Yin et al., 1995). Wave transmission across macroscopic damage features (fractures) in rocks has been extensively studied. Examples of contributions include Pyrak-Nolte et al. (1990a, b), Zhao et al. (2006), Kurtulus et al. (2012), Huang et al. (2014) and Yang et al. (2018). These studies showed that waves propagating parallel to the normal of the fractures are attenuated, as the fractures act as a low-pass filter with significant reflection and refraction taking place at the fracture surface. These aforementioned studies provide a foundation for predicting wave propagation behavior, however, in all these studies the damage was macroscopic and artificially induced, and the material medium immediately adjacent to the fracture was assumed to be homogeneous (Pyrak-Nolte, 1996; Pyrak-Nolte & Kowalsky, 1997). This is in contrast to the fact that when a brittle rock is progressively loaded to failure, damage accumulates randomly in a spatially heterogeneous and diffuse manner with the macroscopic fracture plane (large relative to the probing ultrasonic wavelength (λ)) not developing until after the failure stress is reached, as proven by studies on the micromechanics of brittle failure in rocks (Brace, 1963; Lockner et al., 1991; Menendez et al., 1996; Diederichs, 2003). Therefore, “damage” in the context of present paper, refers to the nucleation of sub-wavelength ($D \ll \lambda$) microcracks which are diffuse and heterogeneously distributed within the rock volume, such that the ultrasonic transmission is primarily affected by the dispersion (scattering) of the waves around the distributed microcracks (Tapponnier & Brace, 1976; Gao et al., 2001; Zuo et al., 2005; Diederichs & Martin, 2010; Treiber et al., 2010; Zhu & Shao, 2017).

Several experimental studies have been conducted over the years utilizing ultrasonic attributes (velocity and attenuation) as a tool for implicit characterization of microcrack evolution in laboratory scale rock specimens (Walsh, 1966; Nur & Simmons, 1969; Nur, 1971; Gupta, 1973; Rao & Ramana, 1974; Lockner et al., 1977; Sayers et al., 1990; Scott et al., 1993; Wulff et al., 1999; Couvreur et al., 2001; Pellet et al., 2007; Ghazvinian, 2015; Modiriasari et al., 2017; Shirole et al., 2017; Barnhoorn et al., 2018; Harnett et al., 2018). Based on these studies, it can be concluded that wave attenuation (amplitude) is a potential indicator of the extent of damage in rocks with attenuation increasing as damage proliferates in a rock

volume. Walsh (1966), Kuster & Toksoz (1974), Hudson (1981), Sayers et al. (1990), Wulff et al. (1999) and Harnett et al. (2018) focused on characterizing the damage (stress-induced microcracking) in rock specimens through the use of crack density, which was evaluated by the use of analytical models that relate velocity changes to density of cracks in the volume of the rock. Wulff et al. (1999) identified a near-linear correlation between amplitude attenuation and the crack density in the specimens. A key feature missing from these aforementioned studies is the lack of explicit evidence while associating material damage with the transmission of the ultrasonic waves. The major challenge in understanding the transmission of ultrasonic waves in progressively damaged intact rock specimens is the heterogeneous (diffuse) distribution of damage that develops under load because of the grain-scale heterogeneity of rocks (Ferrero et al., 2008; Tang & Hudson, 2010; Dautriat et al., 2011). Philippidis & Aggelis (2005), Chaix et al. (2006), and Aggelis & Shiotani (2007) all studied ultrasonic wave attenuation in highly heterogeneous cementitious materials containing randomly distributed inclusions for $D \ll \lambda$, and found strong attenuation and distortion of the waves due to the presence of the inclusions which acted as the scattering source. However, the relationship between stress-induced strain heterogeneity (the primary cause of microcracking in rocks) and ultrasonic wave transmission is an area which has yet to be explicitly studied. Considering the increasing number of studies utilizing active seismic techniques (ultrasonic) for the assessment of material damage (both in research, and, in practical applications), it is imperative to improve our understanding of the impacts of distributed damage on wave attenuation. Therefore, there is need to develop experimental approaches to study the influence of stress-induced damage on the wave propagation behavior in rock specimens. This is challenging, as laboratory tests require the rock specimens to be destroyed, and also because it is difficult to measure strain distributions in real-time throughout rock specimens under load (Peng et al., 2017). To overcome these challenges, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) can be implemented, as it can provide displacement and strain-fields across a stressed rock specimen surface in small time increments and without contacting the specimen (Sutton et al., 2009; Song et al., 2013; Bourcier et al., 2013).

In this study, the 2D-DIC technique has been employed in combination with ultrasonic monitoring to continuously track changes in ultrasonic wave attenuation (amplitude) along with the development of strains across the surface of the intact specimens of Lyons sandstone (LS) that are stressed under uniaxial loading conditions. In particular, the changes in the strains along the localized areas where the ultrasonic imaging is conducted have been studied. This study provides experimental validation of the primary material deformation mechanisms that have the most significant effect on the ultrasonic signal changes.

2. DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION (2D-DIC)

2D-DIC is one of the most prevalent full-field non-destructive non-contact optical methods for the measurement of in-plane displacement and strain fields (Sutton et al., 2009; Dautriat et al., 2011; Hedayat

et al., 2014b). 2D-DIC provides full-field displacements and strains by comparing the digital images of the specimen surface in the un-deformed (or reference) and deformed states. 2D-DIC has several advantages including simple experimental set-up and specimen preparation (requiring only one fixed camera perpendicular to the object surface), the ability to work in ambient light with no special illumination, and ability to accurately measure displacement and strain fields (Hedayat & Walton, 2017).

2.1 Displacement-field measurement

In DIC analysis, a stochastic pattern of gray-scale values is typically required to be applied to the region of material where deformation is to be quantified (Schwartz et al., 2013). The stochastic nature of the gray-scale values facilitates variation of gray-scale values over all the pixels of an image, which enables improved image correlation. In routine implementation of the 2D-DIC method, the reference image is specified at first, which is further divided into small square groups of pixels called subsets, and the distance between each subset is specified – this leads to the formation of a virtual subset field (grid) on the reference image (Schwartz et al., 2013). The reason why a square subset is selected for matching, rather than an individual pixel, is that the subset containing a wider variation in gray-scale levels will distinguish itself from other subsets, and can therefore be more uniquely identified in the deformed image (Sutton et al., 2009; Pan et al., 2009a; Hedayat et al., 2014a). The basic principle of the DIC method is to locate the subsets in the deformed images representing local areas of the specimen, initially defined in the reference image, with the assumption that the grey-scale values in the subsets are preserved during the transformation associated with the deformation (Bourcier et al., 2013). The degree of similarity between the reference subset and the deformed subset is evaluated using a statistical correlation criterion with respect to the displacement characterizing the transformation (for more details the reader is encouraged to read Sutton et al., 2009). The peak position in the distribution of the correlation coefficient defines the position of the deformed subset with respect to the reference subset, which assists in the estimation of the displacement (transformation) between the reference subset and the deformed subset (Hedayat et al., 2014b). The displacement computed from the correlation procedure is then assigned to the center of the subset (grid). The same procedure is automated and repeated for other virtual subsets (grids) present over the specimen surface on the reference and deformed images for the computation of the full-field displacements across the surface of the material at the selected grid points.

2.2 Strain-field measurement

Detailed investigation of the mechanical behavior of materials requires strain measurements at multiple points, and for this reason, it is of value to obtain strain maps covering the entire specimen surface. However, the mathematical numerical differentiation process for computation of strains from a raw

displacement field is considered an inconsistent operation (Luo et al., 2005), as direct differentiation of the estimated (noisy) displacements can amplify the noise contained in the computed displacements, making the resultant strains unreliable (for details refer to Pan et al., 2009a). To overcome this issue, the normal procedure in the calculation of the strains is to smooth the computed displacement field first, and then subsequently differentiate it to calculate the strain fields. This has led to the development of several smoothing techniques, of which the pointwise local least squares fitting technique is most practical because of its ease of use, ability to process data obtained at discontinuities (boundary, hole, cracks, etc.), and the ability to achieve high precision strain measurements (Wattrisse et al., 2001; Pan et al., 2009a, b). In the local least squares fitting technique, a local strain calculation window is defined around the grid point where the strain has to be estimated, and the displacement distribution in the strain calculation window is approximated as a linear plane. The locally linear approximation of the displacement distribution in the strain calculation window aids in removal of noise from the displacement data, thus improving accuracy in the calculation of the strain-field (Pan et al., 2009a). The calculation of strains from the displacement field is based on the standard Lagrangian approach of continuum mechanics, which relates position $\delta(X)$ of some material particle (P in Figure 1) in a reference or initial configuration at time $t=0$ to its position $\delta'(X')$ in the current or deformed configuration at any time t (Dual & Schwarz, 2012; Bourcier et al., 2013). The Lagrangian strain tensor E^* , which facilitates strain measurement when strains are not infinitesimal during the deformation process (Wriggers, 2016), is computed from the displacement gradient ∇u per Equations 1 and 2

$$E^* = \frac{1}{2} [(\nabla u)^T + (\nabla u) + (\nabla u) \cdot (\nabla u)^T] \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla u = \frac{\partial u_p}{\partial X_q} \quad (p, q \in x, y \text{ (} z=0 \text{ for a 2D case)}) \quad (2)$$

The strains along x and y directions are computed from the following equations (Chu et al., 1985; Tung et al., 2008):

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_x} \right)^2 \right] \\ \varepsilon_{yy} &= \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_y} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_y} \right)^2 \right] \\ \varepsilon_{xy} &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_y} + \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_x} \right] + \left[\left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_x} \cdot \frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_x} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial X_y} \cdot \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial X_y} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Based on the results obtained from Eqn. (3), the major and minor principal strains (ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} , respectively) can be calculated.

Figure 1. A solid body moving from its reference configuration $\delta(X)$ to the current configuration $\delta'(X')$ from time $t=0$ to any time t . The position of the material point P with respect to the global coordinate system (x, y, z) is X in the reference configuration and X' in the current configuration.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

3.1 Material

Three uniaxial compression experiments were conducted on prismatic specimens of intact Lyons sandstone, and 2D-DIC and LUT procedures were synchronously implemented on each of the specimens for the non-destructive evaluation of damage evolution at increasing levels of stress. For the purpose of presentation of the experimental results, the tested samples are labelled as LSP-1, LSP-2, and LSP-3, where LSP stands for “Lyons Sandstone Prismatic. A computer-controlled servo-hydraulic loading machine by Controls Group Inc. was used for uniaxially loading the prismatic Lyons sandstone specimens in axial displacement feedback by advancing a piston against the specimen at a rate of $1 \mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ (Figures 2, 3a). Displacement feedback mode provided the ability to control the deformation of the rock specimens close to their uniaxial compressive strength (UCS), which helped to protect the ultrasonic transducers from damage. Linear Variable Differential Transformers (LVDTs) were used for recording the overall axial deformation of the rock specimens.

The Lyons sandstone was obtained from Lyons, Colorado, which is in the front range of the Colorado Rocky Mountains (United States). It is aeolian in origin and was formed through the long-term consolidation of moderately sorted fine-grained quartz sand dunes (Thompson, 1949; Ross et al., 2010; Mighani et al., 2016; Shirole et al., 2017, 2018b). Because of this, Lyons sandstone is primarily composed of quartz (85-90%) with some presence of clay minerals (10-12%) (Ross et al., 2010; Shukla et al., 2014; Henao, 2017). The sandstone block acquired for the present study was quarried from a depth of 5 m below the ground surface. Prismatic specimens of Lyons sandstone 150 mm long (longitudinal axis), 75 mm wide

(transverse axis) and 25 mm thick were prepared from the same block of the Lyons sandstone (Figure 2). The prismatic shape of specimens facilitated a planar surface which is necessary for accurate in-plane 2D-DIC measurements, and it also ensured that the surface strains are representative of the broader specimen deformation (Ferrero et al., 2008; Sutton et al., 2009). The longitudinal axis of the test specimens was normal to the weakly developed bedding plane of the sample block; Lyons sandstone shows a low degree of anisotropy (Mighani et al., 2016). All the peripheral surfaces of the specimens were smooth, flat and leveled to within 0.01 mm under dry conditions using mechanized grinding. Lyons sandstone has an average grain size of about 190 μm (Xu et al., 2006a; Bathija et al., 2009; Ross et al., 2010; Shukla et al., 2014; Mighani et al., 2016, Henao, 2017). The bulk density of Lyons sandstone specimens was 2.52 g/cm^3 , which is similar to the value reported by Xu et al. (2006a). Porosity analysis using a 24 μm Computed Tomography (CT) scan machine on an entire specimen (LSP-1) indicated an average porosity of 4.5%, which is reasonably consistent with the porosity value of 7% as reported by Xu et al. (2006a) and Henao (2017), who employed the Archimedes method and the Boyle's Law Porosimeter method, respectively, for evaluation of the porosity.

Figure 2. The experimental set-up used for synchronously capturing the geophysical signatures of damage using the 2D-DIC and LUT procedures. (1) CCD camera; (2) loading frame; (3) Linear Variable Differential Transformer (LVDT); (4) pulse generator; (5) source pulse box; (6) receiver pulse box; (7) NI-5142 digitizer scope; and (8) Speckled specimen with the transducer assembly, whose close-up view is shown as well, in which, (8a) source transducer, (8b) receiver transducer, and, (8c) IRWIN clamps.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the 2D-DIC set-up for in-plane full-field measurement of displacements. (a) 2D-DIC set-up viewed perpendicular to the camera axis. (b) Speckled front-face of the prismatic specimen captured by the camera with the location of the three ultrasonic transducers pairs on the specimen; viewed co-axially to the camera axis. (c) Typical beam pattern of the 5 MHz longitudinal transducers. The wave characteristics have been calculated per the guidelines provided by Yin et al. (1995), Basu & Aydin (2006), and Olympus Ultrasonic Transducers Technical Notes (2011).

3.2 2D-Digital image correlation (DIC) set-up

2D-DIC was implemented on each of the Lyons sandstone specimens to generate a full-field map of strains across the specimen surfaces at increasing stress levels. A stochastic pattern of gray-scale values (speckle pattern) on the surface of the rock specimens was produced by spray-painting the surface of the specimens to be imaged by a multicolor paint from Rust-Oleum (Sutton et al., 2009; Hedayat, 2013). To ensure a high-quality speckle pattern, the surface of the rock specimens was cleaned from any visible contaminant (oil, grit, etc.) prior to painting. The paint was applied just prior (2 hours) to the experiment so as to maintain maximum adherence of the paint to the specimen in high strain regions, as recommended by Sutton et al. (2009). The uniqueness of the speckle pattern on a specimen surface is fundamental to the accuracy in the correlation process and can be the dominant source of background noise (Lin & Labuz, 2013). Therefore,

two basic features of the prepared speckle pattern were checked to determine its suitability before testing: (1) the distribution of intensity values in the speckle pattern, and (2) the speckle size (Sutton et al., 2009). The speckle pattern produced on the surface of LSP-2 prior to testing is shown in Figure 4a, and the distributions of the gray-scale intensity values for the speckle patterns on each of the specimens are shown in Figure 4b. In practical applications, an optimal speckle pattern for DIC analysis should have a relatively well-distributed histogram of the intensity values over the intensity range from 50 to 220 (Sharpe, 2008; Lin & Labuz, 2013). Accordingly, the values shown in Figure 4b are consistent with the requirement of an optimal speckle pattern for accurate measurement of displacements through DIC (Sharpe, 2008; Lin & Labuz, 2013). In our experimental set-up, one pixel in the digital image corresponded to 100 μm in the physical space. In an optimal speckle pattern, each speckle should be imaged by at least 3 pixels for proper intensity pattern reconstruction during the image correlation process (Sutton et al., 2007, 2009; Hedayat et al., 2014a). The applied speckle size by spray-painting the specimen surface ranged from 300-400 μm (Hedayat, 2013; Hedayat et al., 2014a, b; Hedayat & Walton, 2017), further ensuring the suitability and uniqueness of the produced speckle patterns on the specimen surfaces for an accurate image correlation process.

Figure 4. (a) Digital image of the speckle pattern produced on specimen LSP-2 through spray painting. (b) The distribution of gray-scale intensity values in the speckle patterns generated on the surfaces of the three Lyons sandstone specimens LSP-1, LSP-2, and LSP-3.

During uniaxial compressive loading, digital images of the speckled surfaces of the specimens were captured in real-time. A Grasshopper (Point Grey) CCD (Charged Coupled Device) camera with 2448 by 2048 square pixels in combination with a Fujinon lens of 35 mm focal length (Model CF35HA-1) was used. The FlyCapture SDK software was used to control the camera and the image acquisition rate, while the zoom, aperture and focus of the lens were manually controlled. The camera and the lens were designed to image the entire speckled surface ($150 \times 75 \text{ mm}^2$) of each specimen. The camera was mounted at a distance of 800 mm (z_c) from the specimen, with the axis of the camera parallel to the surface normal of the specimen as shown Figure 3a. The distance of 800 mm was also chosen so as to keep the error in the DIC measurements due to the out-of-plane deformations (Δz) below the prescribed limit of $\Delta z/z_c \sim 10^{-4}$ (Modiriasari et al., 2017). Before each test, image artifacts such as dust on the lens of the camera and local areas of reflection on the object surface were also minimized (Hedayat et al., 2014a).

3.3 Linear ultrasonic testing (LUT) set-up

As the full-field strains across the surfaces of the uniaxially loaded prismatic specimens were measured in real-time using 2D-DIC, LUT measurements were concurrently made at three locations along the height of the specimens. The locations of the three ultrasonic source-receiver arrays (UIA-1, UIA-2, and, UIA-3) along the longitudinal axis of the specimen are shown in Figure 3b, where UIA (Ultrasonic Imaging Area) is the volume of the specimen illuminated by an ultrasonic beam. Videoscan longitudinal wave transducers (V-103) from Olympus NDT, Inc. were used in the study as the source and receiver of the ultrasonic waves. The ultrasonic transducers have a diameter of 6 mm and a central frequency of 5 MHz. A pulse generator from Olympus NDT, Inc. was used as the active source of longitudinal pulse generation (through an excitation voltage of 400 V), while the signal digitization was performed using a National Instruments (NI) digitizer (5142 board) (Figure 2). The pulse generator was regulated to produce a negative square pulse with a central frequency of 5 MHz every 200 μ s, and a LabVIEW-controlled active NI system was used to digitize the ultrasonic waveforms at a sampling frequency of 100 MHz (for details, refer to Shirole et al., 2017). The 200 μ s pulse frequency allowed each ultrasonic pulse to reach the receiver transducer before the propagation of the next pulse, which in turn ensured clear first arrivals of the transmitted pulses. 100 ultrasonic pulses were averaged and stacked on top of each other to produce a higher signal to noise ratio, and the final averaged signal was acquired near-continuously at 1 Hz frequency. The characteristics of the ultrasonic waves (nominal wavelength, P-wave velocity, and seismic beam diameter) based on the transducer properties for the 5 MHz transducers used in the study are shown in Table 1. The wavelength was calculated using the transducer central frequency (Basu & Aydin, 2006). The nominal wavelength of the ultrasonic wave is 930 μ m (Table 1), which is approximately 5 times the grain size (190 μ m) of Lyons sandstone. The typical beam pattern of the ultrasonic signals produced by the 5 MHz transducers is also shown in Figure 3c, corresponding to the signal characteristics given in Table 1. Figure 3c shows that spreading (beam spread) of the ultrasonic signals is not significant for the transducers used in the present study, and therefore the ultrasonic signals in each of the UIA regions are not expected to be influenced by the signals in adjacent UIA regions.

Table 1. Characteristics of the ultrasonic waves propagating through the Lyons sandstone specimens. The wave characteristics have been calculated per the guidelines provided by Yin et al. (1995), Basu & Aydin (2006), and Olympus Ultrasonic Transducers Technical Notes (2011).

Transducer Central Frequency (MHz)	Element Diameter (mm)	P-wave Velocity (m/s)	Nominal Wavelength (mm)	Near-Field (mm)	Beam Spread Angle (θ°)
5	6	4637	0.93	9.0	8.0

All the transducers were placed on the two longitudinal sides of the prismatic specimens using rubber-padded clamps from IRWIN, which applied a lateral stress of approximately 0.01 MPa on the transducers (Figure 2). This amount of stress assisted in maintaining reliable and reproducible contact between the transducer element and the rock surface. Considering the high uniaxial compressive strength (UCS) of the specimens (190 MPa), a lateral stress of 0.01 MPa is not expected to affect the overall specimen behavior, and therefore it is reasonable to consider the overall loading condition applied to the specimens as uniaxial. This is consistent with the methodology of Modiriasari et al. (2015; 2017), who applied an identical level of lateral stress on the transducers and considered the specimen loading conditions to be uniaxial. To reduce the transmission losses due to the impedance mismatch at the rock-transducer contact area (seismic impedance of the transducer element is 35.9 MPa-s/m (Cheeke, 2016), and that of Lyons sandstone is 11.4 MPa-s/m), oven-baked honey was used as the coupling medium between the transducer and rock surface. Honey was chosen because of its relatively viscous nature, and because it is widely considered to be the best coupling medium for longitudinal wave propagation (Couvreur & Thimus, 1996; Hedayat, 2013; Modiriasari et al., 2017). The baking process helps in removal of the air pockets present in the honey (Couvreur & Thimus, 1996; Basu & Aydin, 2006; Modiriasari et al., 2015). In particular, the honey was dehydrated in an oven at 100 °C for 90 min. Prior to application of the honey, the surface of the rock specimen was smoothed to offset minor surface roughness, and was covered with an adhesive plastic film to prevent the penetration of honey into the rock pores (Basu & Aydin, 2006; Hedayat, 2013; Modiriasari et al., 2017). The thickness of the coupling medium should be a small fraction of the wavelength of the ultrasonic wave to reduce the effect of impedance mismatch (Basu & Aydin, 2006); in the experiments conducted in this study, an average honey layer thickness of 30 μm was maintained, which is consistent with this requirement since the wavelength of the ultrasonic wave is 930 μm (Table 1). Before starting any test, the transducer assembly (Figure 2, 3b) with honey coupling was allowed to equilibrate for 1 h, to ensure that any time-dependent artifacts associated with the coupling between the transducers and the specimen were eliminated. After the honey coupling, the Lyons sandstone specimens were uniaxially loaded, and the full waveforms (100 μs duration) of the transmitted ultrasonic signals were continuously acquired at 1 Hz using the LabVIEW-controlled data acquisition system in-sync with the 2D-DIC image capture procedure. Figure 5 shows the transmitted ultrasonic signals at different levels of loading; in examining these signals, the effects of damage on the ultrasonic waves can be observed. At low levels of loading (e.g. 25% of UCS), there is an increase in the amplitude and reduction in the travel time of the ultrasonic signals when compared with the signal under a no stress condition. With further increase in the load magnitude (and associated damage formation), the ultrasonic signals begin to lose energy (reduction in amplitude), and wave arrival is delayed (compare the signal at no stress with signals at 80% and 95% of the UCS).

Figure 5. Comparison of the typical longitudinal ultrasonic signals at different magnitudes of the failure stress (UCS) for LSP-1. Compare the signal at no stress (purple) with the signal at 95% of UCS (blue).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Assessment of the 2D-DIC results

2D-DIC, as described in Section 2, was used to quantify the full-field displacement and strains on the specimen surface. The correlation (2D-DIC) procedure is executed on digital images where the measurements are in pixel-space, meaning a constant magnification factor (M), is commonly applied to transform the pixel-based measurements to their respective physical dimensions (Hedayat et al., 2014a). Taking into account the fixed size of the CCD camera array (2448×2048 pixels), and the fixed field of view (as the image captures the entire specimen surface of 150×75 mm²), a constant magnification factor of $M=100$ $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ was established (Figure 4a).

The images acquired during the uniaxial compression tests were analyzed using VIC-2D DIC software to extract the displacements and strains across the specimen surface. The analysis procedure in VIC-2D DIC software requires two inputs: subset size (also known as grid size, as discussed in Section 2) and step size, as described by Correlated Solutions (2010b). Sutton et al. (2007) suggested that a subset should contain at least 3 speckles. Considering 4 pixels per speckle width, the minimum size of subset needs to be at least 12 pixels. To avoid selecting a value that was too small, a subset size of 15 was selected (Sutton et al., 2007). Hedayat et al. (2014a) suggested to avoid the use of large subset sizes as it can lead to considerable errors in displacement measurements, and that is why the implementation of a larger subset size was avoided. Step size (in pixels) defines how far apart the tracking points are placed in the specimen (Patel & Martin,

2018b), and the step size is typically chosen such that it is smaller than half the subset size (Hedayat et al., 2014a). Considering the required computation time for the DIC analysis, a step size of 5 pixels was selected. This ensured that the subsets overlapped each other and provided oversampling for added accuracy in the measurement of the displacement field (Hedayat et al., 2014b).

To assess the accuracy of the 2D-DIC measurements, the axial strains acquired by the 2D-DIC procedure and using LVDTs were compared for each of the uniaxial compression tests throughout the loading history. The 2D-DIC full-field axial strains were averaged at each stress level across the whole surface of the specimen for comparison purposes. Figure 6 shows the percent failure stress (stress as a percentage of UCS) versus axial-strain plots obtained from the LVDTs and the 2D-DIC procedure for specimens LSP-1, LSP-2 and LSP-3. To evaluate the effect of the subset size on the DIC measurements, an additional specimen (LSP-0) was uniaxially loaded with DIC measurements being processed using different subset sizes. From Figure 6, it can be seen that the DIC measurements were overall consistent with the LVDT measurements, confirming the accuracy of the DIC set-up as a whole. Figure 6a (LSP-0) shows that changes in the subset size (SS-15 to SS-79) do not significantly affect the DIC measurements. For further comparison, the slope of the percent failure stress-axial strain plots of Figure 6 at 50% of failure load for the DIC and LVDT measurements are given in Table 2. The stress at 50% of the failure stress was chosen for comparing the corresponding slopes of the percent failure stress-axial strain plots obtained from the DIC and LVDTs, as it is expected to be in the linear portion of the axial stress-axial strain plots (Fairhurst & Hudson, 1999; ASTM Standard D3148-02, 2001), and is similar to the procedure followed by Patel & Martin (2018a, b). The percentage difference in the slopes calculated by the two measurements increases above 10% for LSP-0 for subset sizes of 61 and 79, while it remains below 10% for smaller subsets further confirming the suitability of subset size of 15 pixels for the image correlation (Table 2). The percentage difference in the slopes is below 10% for specimens LSP-1, LSP-2 and LSP-3 as well. Patel & Martin (2018a, b) considered up to 10% difference in the slopes of the axial stress–axial strain plots calculated by the LVDT and DIC as acceptable, and therefore, the DIC measurements, obtained by the DIC set-up designed in this study, can be used with confidence.

Figure 6. Comparison of the percent failure stress-axial strain plots obtained from the LVDT and the 2D-DIC measurements respectively. The “SS” values in the legend represent subset size, ranging from 15 pixels to 79 pixels. The DIC measurements shown at each stress level were averaged across the surface of the prismatic specimens.

Table 2. Comparison of the slopes of the percent failure-axial strain plots obtained from the DIC and LVDT measurements at 50% of the failure stress. SS in the table denotes the subset size (SS) used in the image correlation procedure.

Specimen ID	Slope ($\times 10^4$)		Percentage Difference (%) ($\text{LVDT}_{\text{Slope}} - \text{DIC}_{\text{Slope}}) * 100 / \text{LVDT}_{\text{Slope}}$
	DIC	LVDT	
LSP-0	0.037 (SS-15)	0.040	7.5
	0.036 (SS-31)		10.0
	0.035 (SS-49)		12.5
	0.035 (SS-61)		12.5
	0.034 (SS-79)		15.0
LSP-1	0.040 (SS-15)	0.043	7.0
LSP-2	0.029 (SS-15)	0.029	0
LSP-3	0.029 (SS-15)	0.028	3.5

4.2 2D-DIC full-field strains under uniaxial loading

Figure 7 shows the strain field for the specimen LSP-1 at different stress levels obtained through the image correlation process. The major principal strain (ϵ_{11}) results from uniaxial compression of the specimen along its longitudinal axis (along specimen long dimension in Figure 7), while the minor principal strain (ϵ_{22}) evolves because of the Poisson's effect, with the material expanding in the lateral direction (Figure 7). Consequently, the distribution of the ϵ_{11} strain field shows dominantly a series of primarily sub-horizontal strain concentrations in comparison to the sub-vertical features in the ϵ_{22} strain field. At low level of stress (25% of UCS), the ϵ_{11} strain map is fairly homogenous along the specimen surface, while the ϵ_{22} strain map shows some non-uniformity in the strain distribution (Figure 7). The strain localization in the ϵ_{22} strain-field at such low levels of stress can be attributed to the low crack initiation (CI) damage threshold (25-30% of UCS) of Lyons sandstone, as reported by Shirole et al. (2018b). At higher levels of stress (50% and 75% of UCS), both the ϵ_{11} and ϵ_{22} distributions show a distinct increase in strain concentration, which becomes most evident at 90% of UCS. Whereas the average specimen axial strain (ϵ_{yy}) is 2200 $\mu\epsilon$ at 90% of UCS for LSP-1, the DIC measurements distinctly show areas where the strain is above this magnitude (please compare Figures 6b and 7a). This strain-field heterogeneity is consistent with expected specimen behavior based on the findings of Diederichs (2003).

Figure 7. Full-field profile of the major (ϵ_{11}) and minor (ϵ_{22}) principal strains obtained by 2D-DIC at different stress levels; (a) major (ϵ_{11}) principal strain; (b) minor (ϵ_{22}) principal strain for the specimen LSP-1. Positive (+) and negative (-) strains represent contraction and extension, respectively.

As Lyons sandstone is expected to show brittle behavior (because of its high quartz content and the ambient temperature and pressure conditions used during testing), the dominant failure mechanism is the formation of microcracks due to the extensile strains, with the cracks oriented sub-parallel to the major principal stress direction (Wulff et al., 1999; Lan et al., 2010; Walton, 2014; Ghazvinian, 2015; Mighani et al., 2016). The map of the ϵ_{22} strain field, which is tensile in nature, shows regions of strain concentrations which are sub-parallel to the loading direction, meaning that the microcracks are oriented sub-parallel to the specimen longitudinal axis (Figure 7b). Considering the fact that cracking associated with local tensile stresses (sub-vertically oriented) is the primary deformation mechanism for brittle rocks, the distribution of strains and its effect on the ultrasonic signatures was studied by analyzing the ϵ_{22} tensile strain field in the UIA regions

(Diederichs, 1999; Ferrero et al., 2008). Accordingly, the strain distribution on the DIC grid-points in the local UIA regions (UIA-1, UIA-2 and UIA-3) at different levels of loading for the three Lyons sandstone specimens are shown in Figure 8. At small loads (see results for 25% of UCS in Figure 8), the distribution of strain has a small standard deviation (0.5 mε), with most of the DIC grid-points concentrated around 1 mε. With an increase in loading (50% of UCS), the spread in the histogram increases (standard deviation in strain distribution is approximately 1 mε), indicating magnification of the maximum extensile strain magnitude on the DIC grid-points. The spread in the distribution of the histograms becomes even more evident at 90% of UCS (standard deviation is approximately 1.5 mε), which is consistent with the increased localization and heterogeneity in the strain field at increasing levels of damage (Diederichs, 1999). The spread in the histograms is associated with the increase in the number of DIC grid-points with higher magnitudes of tensile strains. The appearance of compressive strain in some of the DIC grid-point in the tensile ε_{22} field can be attributed to the heterogeneous nature of strain redistribution at the grain scale (Diederichs, 1999). In order to evaluate the intensity of extension in the three UIA regions, an apparent tensile (AT) strain (ε_{AT}^T), similar to the strain metrics proposed by Mazars (1986) and Song et al. (2013), is used:

$$\varepsilon_{AT}^T = \left| \sum_{j=1}^N \langle \varepsilon_{22,j} \rangle \right| \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon_{22,j}$ is the minor principal strain at DIC grid-point j , N is the number of grid-points (2261 in this study), and $\langle \bullet \rangle$ are brackets indicating the computation of negative part (tensile component) of the argument only. The apparent tensile strain (ε_{AT}^T) facilitates the computation of the tensile strains only, which is the dominant cause of failure in rocks. The superscript T on the left-hand-side of Eqn. (4) signifies the total (T) nature of the apparent tensile strain, including both the elastic (E) and non-elastic (NE) components of the tension present in the material.

Figure 8. Histograms showing the distribution of strain in the local UIA regions for the three Lyons sandstone specimens; (a) LSP-1; (b) LSP-2; and (c) LSP-3. Positive (+) and negative (-) strains represent contraction and extension, respectively.

In traditional intact rock testing, the crack initiation stress (CI) is commonly related to the development of non-elastic strains in the material, as material at the grain-scale is expected to yield beyond the critical tensile strain limit, ϵ_c (Bridgman, 1912; Stacey, 1981; Eberhardt, 1998; Eberhardt et al., 1998, 1999; Ghazvinian et al., 2011; Ghazvinian, 2015). Consequently, areas experiencing microcracking are expected to be characterized by ϵ_{22} values above some critical threshold at which cracking initiates. With this in mind, and given that local cracks will be most significant in controlling LUT parameters, it is important to evaluate

the non-elastic (NE) component of the apparent tension (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}). For this purpose, the critical tensile strain limit (ϵ_c) above which cracking initiates was estimated as shown in Figure 9 and described in the following paragraph.

To evaluate the critical value of extensile strain limit (ϵ_c), it is important to consider the scale of the strain measurements obtained, as rock is a heterogeneous brittle material (Lan et al., 2010; Peng et al., 2017). A rock's microstructural heterogeneity produces a spatially inconsistent strain response to the external stress field, which causes multi-scale (specimen-scale to grain-scale) fluctuations/localizations in strain redistribution (Blair & Cook, 1998; Bornert et al., 2010; Dautriat et al., 2011). Global mean field (GMF) or specimen-scale measurements assume that the strains released from a broken mesoscopic unit are shared uniformly by all intact units (Xia et al., 2002; Xu et al., 2005). At reduced scales of measurement, localized strain fluctuations become much more evident as the strains from a broken unit flow locally only to the neighboring units (Xu et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2006b). Consequently, the critical value of extensile strain (ϵ_c) was evaluated at three scales: (i) specimen-scale; (ii) pixel-scale; and (iii) grain-scale (Figure 9).

At the specimen-scale (global), the widely accepted Stacey (1981) strain criterion was employed for evaluation of ϵ_c (Figure 9a). This criterion is based on the expectation that the strain (ϵ_c) indicating initiation of extensile microcracks would be reflected by a small but visually observable change in the slope of the vertical strain (ϵ_{yy}) vs lateral (ϵ_{xx}) strain plot, as the extension microcracks initiate in planes parallel to the vertical strain direction (ϵ_{yy}) causing the specimen to expand rapidly in lateral (ϵ_{xx}) direction. Figure 9a shows the plot of ϵ_{yy} vs ϵ_{xx} strain for LSP-2, through which the specimen-scale ϵ_c value was estimated to be $-2e-4$ (positive (+) and negative (-) strains represent contraction and extension, respectively). For estimation of ϵ_c at the grain-scale, the tensile cracking limit of the clay cement present between the quartz grains was calculated as shown in Figure 9c (Ross et al., 2010). From this, the grain-scale ϵ_c value was estimated to be $-22e-4$. At the pixel-scale (which depends on the strain resolution of the DIC measurements and is equivalent to 2500 μm in this case), the appropriate value of ϵ_c could be constrained to vary between these two bounds (between specimen-scale and grain-scale).

As Acoustic Emissions (AEs) are released by locally non-elastic deformation events (microcracking), it has been used as an experimental tool for the characterization of the state of microcracking in progressively stressed (uniaxially loaded) rock specimens (Lisjak et al., 2013). Experimental studies have shown that although AE activity occurs continuously throughout a test (specimens under uniaxial load), the beginning of significant AE activity- which arises because of non-elastic deformation- coincides with the CI stress (Eberhardt, 1998). The pixel-scale ϵ_c for calculation of the non-elastic strain was calculated based on this expectation that it will show a significant change at the CI stress threshold, which is similar to the increase in AE (non-elastic deformation) at CI stress. For this, the 35th, 10th and 2nd percentile of strain distribution

(across the specimen surface) as a function of loading was plotted (Figure 9b). Ultimately, the 2nd percentile of the strain distribution at the crack initiation (CI) threshold was used as the critical strain limit at pixel scale (-16e-4). The 2nd percentile of strain-distribution was chosen because its evolution as a function of loading was similar to the evolution of acoustic events (non-elastic deformation) in rock specimens put under uniaxial load (Eberhardt, 1998; Ghazvinian, 2015), and also because its evolution was consistent with the evolution of extensile cracks in uniaxially loaded specimens as shown in numerical studies conducted by Diederichs (1999), Nicksiar (2012) and Farahmand & Diederichs (2015). While the value of ϵ_c determined is approximate in nature, it provides a starting point for the purposes of calculating the strains associated with cracked elements (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}). With this in mind, Figure 9b shows that at the pixel scale, ϵ_c is -16e-4. After determination of ϵ_c , the non-elastic component of the apparent tension (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) was evaluated as per Eqn. (5):

$$\epsilon_{AT}^{NE} = \left| \sum_{j=1}^N \epsilon_{22,j} \right| \text{ where, } \epsilon_{22,j} \leq \epsilon_c \quad (5)$$

Figure 9. The procedure followed for the calculation of the critical strain limit ϵ_c , where: (a) specimen-scale; (b) pixel-scale (which depends on strain resolution); and (c) grain-scale. ¹Stacey (1981); ²Diederichs (1999); ³Shirole et al. (2018b); ⁴Sharma & Verma (1997); ⁵Tang et al. (2014); ⁶Prat et al. (1995); ⁷Strozyk & Tankiewicz (2016).

Figure 10 shows the evolution of the total and non-elastic apparent tensile strain values with increasing levels of stress for the three UIA locations and for each of the specimens. From Figure 10a, it can be

definitively concluded that the changes in ϵ_{AT}^T with damage follow a specific trend (similar to the evolution of crack density with increasing levels of stress as reported in the study of Wulff et al., 1999). Initially at low levels of stress (0-30% of UCS), a decrease in the total apparent tension ϵ_{AT}^T is observed in all of the three UIA regions. This reduction in the total apparent tension ϵ_{AT}^T can be associated with material hardening during the initial stages of compressive loading due to the rearrangement of the internal grain-structure of the rock, with micro-defects closing and pores collapsing (Nicksiar & Martin, 2012; Bogusz & Bukowska, 2015; Shirole et al., 2018b). Between 25-35% of the UCS, there is an increase in the ϵ_{AT}^T values, which is consistent with the CI threshold of Lyons sandstone (between 20-30% of UCS) (Shirole et al., 2018b). As the loading increases beyond 35-40% of UCS, ϵ_{AT}^T continues to rise gradually. This increase in the total apparent tension (ϵ_{AT}^T) can be linked with the emergence of regions of tensile strain concentration due to the expansion of the material in the lateral direction (see Figure 7b). With further increase in loading, there is an accelerated increase in ϵ_{AT}^T at about 70%-80% of the UCS. This prominent increase in ϵ_{AT}^T is consistent with the formation of trans-granular cracks and microcrack coalescence at the crack damage threshold (CD) of Lyons sandstone (Shirole et al., 2018b). Figure 10b shows the variation in the non-elastic apparent tension (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) with increasing levels of damage for the three UIA locations. The evolution of ϵ_{AT}^{NE} with damage also follows a particular trend similar to the profile of ϵ_{AT}^T . At low levels of stress (0-35% of UCS), ϵ_{AT}^{NE} remains approximately constant, in contrast to the reduction in ϵ_{AT}^T values in the same stress regime. This is consistent with the elastic and undamaged state of the specimens up to the CI limit of the rock specimens (25-30% of UCS). Below CI, the rock specimens are not expected to display inelastic behavior associated with the development of extensile microcracks, and consequently the ϵ_{AT}^{NE} variations are minimal up to CI. With further loading (30-75% of UCS), the ϵ_{AT}^{NE} value increases as the material becomes increasingly non-elastic because of stress-induced microcracking. Overall, ϵ_{AT}^{NE} is more sensitive to damage evolution than ϵ_{AT}^T , as it shows changes on the order of 200-400% over the course of testing in comparison to increases of around 100% in ϵ_{AT}^T .

Figure 10. Variation of (a) total apparent tension ϵ_{AT}^T , and, (b) non-elastic apparent tension ϵ_{AT}^{NE} as a function of loading for the rock specimens LSP-1, 2, 3 at the three UIA locations.

4.3 LUT signatures under uniaxial loading

As shown in Figure 3, LUT measurements were also carried out at three locations along the length of the specimen (UIA-1, UIA-2, and UIA-3), in-sync with the 2D-DIC measurements. In particular, the amplitude of the transmitted ultrasonic waves were analyzed simultaneously with increasing levels of load on the rock specimens. The amplitude of the transmitted seismic wave was calculated as the summation of the absolute maximum and absolute minimum voltage in the time-domain signals (Hedayat et al., 2018). Figure 11 shows the changes induced in the transmitted amplitude of the ultrasonic signals due to the increasing level of uniaxial stress on the specimens. The amplitude of the transmitted ultrasonic waves were normalized with respect to their amplitude at the start of the uniaxial compressive loading similar to the procedure followed by Modiriasari et al. (2017). The trend of the changes in the ultrasonic wave amplitude due to increasing level of loading follow a reasonably consistent trend for all the specimens and for each of the UIA regions (Figure 11). Initially at low levels of load (20%-30% of UCS), an increase in the transmitted amplitude of the ultrasonic waves can be observed for all the specimens, which is consistent with the findings of Gowd (1970) who also observed an increment in the amplitude of the ultrasonic waves in the initial stages of loading. This increase in the amplitude is consistent with the reduction in the total apparent tensile strain ϵ_{AT}^T in the same stress regime (see Figure 10a). The reduction in ϵ_{AT}^T is associated with material hardening which increases the contact area between the grains of the rocks, resulting in an increase in the transmission of the ultrasonic wave amplitude (Liu & Nagel, 1992; Gheibi & Hedayat, 2018). Amplitude attenuation in the ultrasonic waves starts to increase with an increase in the stress magnitude applied on the specimens (30% to 70% of the UCS). This attenuation in the ultrasonic signals can qualitatively be attributed to the formation and initiation of grain-boundary cracks which tend to reduce the wave transmission amplitude due to frictional sliding on the crack surfaces (Gowd, 1970; Rao & Ramana, 1974; Modiriasari et al., 2017). The increase in the total and non-elastic apparent tensile strain at the same stress level is consistent with the formation of extensile cracks over this range of stresses (30% to 70% of the UCS). The amplitude reduces at an accelerated rate as the applied stress on the specimens is increased beyond 70-80% of its failure strength, which can be linked with the increased rate at which the total and non-elastic apparent tensile strain increase starting around the same stress level (see Figure 10).

The results in present work show that the amplitudes drop by 40-80% from their initial value over the course of loading (Figure 11). This observation is consistent with the conclusions of several other studies that attenuation is sensitive to flaws in the medium through which a wave propagates (Walsh, 1966; Gowd, 1970; Gupta, 1973; Rao & Ramana, 1974; Lockner et al., 1977; Modiriasari et al., 2015; Barnhoorn et al., 2018). This is also consistent with the fact that at high frequencies (in the range of MHz) the ultrasonic

wave amplitude is more sensitive to damage than the ultrasonic wave velocity (Pyrak-Nolte et al., 1987a, b; Pyrak-Nolte et al., 1990a, b; Chen et al., 1993; Modiriasari et al., 2017; Barnhoorn et al., 2018).

Figure 11. Variation of ultrasonic wave amplitude as a function of loading for the rock specimens LSP-1, 2, 3 at the three UIA locations.

4.4 Correlation between full-field strains and ultrasonic wave amplitude

Understanding the relationship between the full-field strain-evolution and corresponding changes in the LUT parameters is important for explicitly correlating damage evolution in the rocks with the changes in the LUT parameters. To this end, the ultrasonic wave amplitude has been plotted against the calculated tensile strain quantities at each stress level during the uniaxial experiments (Figure 12). Figure 12 shows that the relationship between the ultrasonic wave amplitude and the apparent tensile strain (ϵ_{AT}^T ; ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) is consistent above the CI threshold for all the specimens; in particular, ultrasonic wave amplitude reduces as the intensity of tensile strain increases in the three UIA regions. In contrast to this, the amplitude shows inconsistent non-linear relationship with the apparent tensile strain below the CI limit. In laboratory-based uniaxial compressive tests, stable microcrack growth initiates only above the CI threshold, and below this threshold stress-induced microcracking is not expected to initiate as the tensile strain intensity is not large enough to induce stable extensile microcracks (Diederichs, 1999; Cai et al., 2004). The absence of microcracks below the CI threshold explains the inconsistent correlation between the ultrasonic wave amplitude and apparent tensile strain (ϵ_{AT}^T ; ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) below CI, as the transmission of ultrasonic waves is only strongly affected by the presence of cracks (Meglis et al., 1996). The inconsistent non-linear correlation up to CI can also be attributed to the low sensitivity of the LUT testing procedure to detect changes in a material medium at low levels of loading (van den Abeele & Visscher, 2000; Shirole et al. 2018a, b).

Figure 12a shows the relationship between the ultrasonic wave amplitude and ϵ_{AT}^T , from which it can be inferred that the ultrasonic wave amplitude reduces as the ϵ_{AT}^T increases in the three UIA regions for stresses above the CI limit. A similar observation can be made from Figure 12b, which shows that increasing non-elastic apparent tensile strains (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) correspond to a reduction in the ultrasonic wave amplitude. In particular, ϵ_{AT}^{NE} shows better correlation with wave amplitude relative to the correlation of ϵ_{AT}^T with wave amplitude (compare Figure 12a and Figure 12b). This is expected because the non-elastic tension (crack formation) in the specimens is expected to influence the transmitted wave to a greater extent than the areas that are deforming elastically under locally tensile stress (Modiriasari et al., 2015). The relatively better correlation of ϵ_{AT}^{NE} with the amplitude is also consistent with the findings of Lockner et al. (1977), who stated that amplitude attenuation is a measure of the non-elastic component of deformation in the medium through which the ultrasonic wave propagates; these results (Figure 12) therefore represent an explicit experimental confirmation of the fundamental observations of Lockner et al. (1977).

Figure 12b shows that the relationship between the non-elastic apparent tensile strain and the ultrasonic wave amplitude above the CI is approximately linear, which is consistent with the findings of Wulff et al. (1999), who also obtained near-linear correlation between amplitude attenuation and analytical velocity-

inverted crack density in the specimens. Lu et al. (2017) also found that the presence of damage attenuates the energy of transmitting ultrasonic waves, and that the dissipation of the ultrasonic energy increases approximately linearly with the damage, which is also consistent with the correlations shown in Figure 12b. Cai & Zhao (2000) also noted that high frequency waves (ultrasonic waves) propagating through a fractured material are attenuated (and slowed), with each of the fractures contributing individually to wave attenuation like a single discrete feature. Similarly, Huang et al. (2014) and Yang et al. (2018) found that fractures lead to the loss in transmission (reduction in amplitude) of the high frequency ultrasonic waves. Based on its definition, any increase in the magnitude of the ε_{AT}^{NE} is analogous to the formation, accumulation and growth of extensile microcracks in the rock specimens. As tensile strain induced microcracks accumulate in the specimen (increasing ε_{AT}^{NE}), more of the ultrasonic wave energy gets dissipated at the microcrack locations, leading to a reduction in the transmitted wave amplitude. The results shown in Figure 12b are consistent with the findings of Modiriasari et al. (2015; 2017) who found that increasing amounts of tensile microcracking led to a reduction in the direct transmitted wave amplitude.

In the case of brittle rocks, most of the microcracking-related damage prior to the failure stress (UCS) is intergranular (between grains), either by widening of pre-existing microcracks or by rupturing of the cementitious grain contacts with the dimensions of the microcracks being similar to the grain size (Zhang et al., 1990; Diederichs, 1999; Hazzard et al., 2000). With this in mind, the size (D) of the majority of the microcrack-related damage features can be considered to be approximately 190 μm (as the average grain size of Lyons sandstone is 190 μm). The wavelength (λ) of the propagating ultrasonic wave is 930 μm (Table 1), which is approximately 5 times of the size of the damage features ($D \ll \lambda$, sub-wavelength damage features). In the limit of $D \ll \lambda$, scattering-related attenuation is significant (Yin et al., 1995; Treiber et al., 2010). As the travelling ultrasonic wave crosses the heterogeneities (microcracks) in the transmitting medium, the wave energy is scattered in many different directions that are different from the original direction of wave propagation, which leads to attenuation in the ultrasonic energy transmitted in the original direction of propagation (Gao et al., 2001; Treiber et al., 2010). This can alternatively be explained as the fact that if a set of microcracks (increasing ε_{AT}^{NE}) exists within the transmitting medium, the ultrasonic signals have a more tortuous propagation path to travel, which subsequently leads to increased dissipation in the energy of the propagating wave (Anugonda et al., 2001; Aggelis & Shiotani, 2007). The attenuation of the ultrasonic waves with increasing magnitude of ε_{AT}^{NE} (microcrack accumulation) can also be related to the dissipation in the ultrasonic energy due to frictional loss at locations of new stress-induced microcracks (Lockner et al., 1977; Wulff et al., 1999; Couvreur et al., 2001). Frictional dissipation of the ultrasonic energy is associated with the work done against friction along the mating faces of the microcracks or grain contacts, as with the passage of a shear or compressional wave the contact area between grains and

microcracks is subjected to a partial sliding motion (Walsh, 1966; Mavko, 1979). As the microcrack density increases, the dissipation in ultrasonic energy due to the friction loss is also expected to increase, which is consistent with the observations of Lockner et al. (1977). The increase in attenuation of the ultrasonic signals as a function of the non-elastic apparent tensile strain (microcracks), with a near-linear correlation as shown in Figure 12, can therefore be associated with the dissipation in the ultrasonic energy due to scattering and friction related wave attenuation mechanisms.

The effect of microcracking on the ultrasonic wave amplitude becomes more evident when comparing the magnitudes of ϵ_{AT}^{NE} for the three UIA regions. The magnitude of ϵ_{AT}^{NE} is consistent for the three UIA regions for LSP-2, and correspondingly the amplitude attenuation for the three UIA regions is also consistent (Figure 12b). For LSP-1 and LSP-3, the magnitude of ϵ_{AT}^{NE} is non-uniform for the three UIA regions, where the greatest reduction in the transmitted signal amplitude corresponds to the highest strain values (UIA-3 for LSP-1, and, UIA-1 and UIA-2 for LSP-3 in Figure 12b). These observations further corroborate the findings of Kurtulus et al. (2012), Modiriasari et al. (2015; 2017), and Yang et al. (2018) that the presence of cracks caused by locally tensile strain concentrations is the primary cause of attenuation in the ultrasonic wave amplitude in intact rock. Furthermore, these results suggest that the selected strain metrics provide a practically useful representation of microcrack damage in rock for the purposes of understanding ultrasonic wave attenuation.

Studies have concluded that changes in ultrasonic amplitude can be a precursor to the evolution of damage in rock specimens with macroscopic flaws (Hedayat et al., 2013; Hedayat et al., 2014a; Modiriasari et al., 2015, 2017). In contrast, there are studies that have shown the capability of ultrasonic signals to objectively define onset of cracking in rocks without any precursors to damage being indicated by the ultrasonic signals (Wulff et al., 1999; Couvreur et al., 2001; Barnhoorn et al., 2018). In the tests conducted in present study, the attenuation in ultrasonic amplitude begins around 25-30% of UCS for the three specimens (Figure 11), which is close to the Crack Initiation (CI) limit of Lyons sandstone (25-30% of UCS). ϵ_{AT}^{NE} , which is a metric of damage as calculated from the surface strain-field, shows a distinct rise around 30% of failure stress for the specimens (Figure 10b). With further loading (30-75% of UCS), the ϵ_{AT}^{NE} value increases as the material becomes increasingly non-elastic because of stress-induced microcracking, with an accelerated increase around 70-80% of UCS (Figure 10b). The amplitude also reduces at an increased rate as the applied stress on the specimens is increased beyond 75% of its failure strength (Figure 11), which can be linked with the increased rate at which the non-elastic apparent tensile strain (ϵ_{AT}^{NE}) increases starting around the same stress level (see Figure 10). From this, it can be concluded that at increased level of damage, the changes in strain-field tend to be near-simultaneous with the changes in the wave attenuations. This can be further confirmed from the near-linear relationship between the ϵ_{AT}^{NE} and the ultrasonic wave amplitude

above the CI (Figure 12b), coherent with the findings of Wulff et al. (1999). This observation is consistent with the studies of Wulff et al. (1999), Couvreur et al. (2001) and Barnhoorn et al. (2018) who found that the changes in ultrasonic signals can be an objective signature of onset (not a precursor) of microcracking in rocks where the damage is diffuse (randomly distributed) and small relative to the ultrasonic wavelength (identical to the scenario in the present study).

Figure 12. Correlation between the ultrasonic wave amplitude and the stress-induced strains in the Lyons sandstone specimens at the three UIA locations, where: (a) total apparent tensile strain (ϵ^T_{AT}); and (b) non-elastic tensile strain (ϵ^{NE}_{AT}) represent the magnitude of the apparent tensile strain.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effect of stress-induced microcracking on the transmission of ultrasonic waves was explicitly analyzed. The 2D-DIC strain measurement approach was employed for evaluation of the progression of full-field surface strains in real-time for brittle rock specimens (Lyons sandstone) subjected to uniaxial loading, and the changes in the strain-field were linked with the changes in the ultrasonic wave amplitude in the localized area illuminated by the ultrasonic beams, referred to as the Ultrasonic Image Area (UIA).

The 2D-DIC full-field strain map showed that the strain-field of the rock specimens becomes increasingly heterogeneous with increasing load on the rock specimens. Based on the fact that cracking related to local extensile strains is the primary deformation mechanism for brittle rocks such as Lyons sandstone, the distribution of strains and its effect on the ultrasonic signatures was studied by analyzing the ε_{22} tensile strain field. In particular, the intensity of extensile strain in the UIA regions was analyzed through the total (ε_{AT}^T) and non-elastic apparent tensile strain (ε_{AT}^{NE}). The non-elastic apparent tensile strain represents the component of the total apparent tensile strain above a critical tensile strain limit (ε_c). The study showed that the total and non-elastic apparent tensile strain follow consistent trends with increasing levels of loading on the rock specimens, with both ε_{AT}^T and ε_{AT}^{NE} increasing significantly very close to failure of the specimens. The trend of changes in ε_{AT}^T with increasing load was similar to the evolution of crack density in rock specimens fractured under anisotropic loading conditions, which suggests that the strain metrics selected in this study can be a useful representation of microcrack damage processes in rocks for the purposes of understanding ultrasonic wave attenuation.

The ultrasonic wave amplitudes for the three UIA regions for each of the rock specimens showed similar trends with respect to load level, with the amplitude increasing at initial levels of loading, and then attenuating with increased load, showing an accelerated attenuation rate close to the failure strength. The attenuation in amplitude was observed to be near-simultaneous with the changes in the surface strains of the specimens because of the minimal thickness of the specimens. The correlation of ultrasonic amplitude with the non-elastic apparent strain was more consistently linear in comparison to its correlation with the total apparent strain. This can be attributed to the fact that non-elastic tension (crack formation) in the specimens is expected to influence the transmitted wave to a greater extent than the areas that are deforming elastically under locally tensile stress, which is consistent with the observations of Lockner et al. (1977). The increase in attenuation of the ultrasonic signals as a function of the non-elastic apparent tensile strain (microcracks) was associated with the dissipation in the ultrasonic energy due to scattering and friction related wave attenuation mechanisms. The near-linear correlation between the ultrasonic amplitude and non-elastic apparent tensile also provided explicit experimental validation of the fact that the presence of

cracks caused by locally tensile strain concentrations is the primary cause of attenuation in the ultrasonic wave amplitude in brittle rocks undergoing stress-induced damage.

NOTE ON DATA AVAILABILITY

Interested readers can obtain the data pertaining to this research article from:

<https://figshare.com/s/848e83f842018f7d2d55>.

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